

On NGSR Closed Sets in Neutrosophic Topological Spaces

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Abstract: The intention of this paper is to introduce the concept of GSR-closed sets in terms of neutrosophic topological spaces. Some of the properties of NGSR-closed sets are obtained. In addition, we inspect NGSR-continuity and NGSR-contra continuity in neutrosophic topological spaces.

Keywords: neutrosophic topology, NGSR-closed set, NGSR-continuous, NGSR-contra continuous mappings.

1. Introduction

In 1965, fuzzy concept was proposed by Zadeh [43] and he studied membership function. Chang [14] developed the theory of fuzzy topology in 1967. The notions of inclusion, union, intersection, complement, relation, convexity, and so forth, are expanded to such sets and several properties of these notions are established by various authors.

Atanassov [10, 11, 12] generalized the idea of fuzzy set to intuitionistic fuzzy set by adding the degree of non-membership. The intuitionistic fuzzy topology was advanced by Coker [16] using the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Intuitionistic fuzzy point was given by Coker et.al [15]. These approaches gave a wide field for exploration in the area of intuitionistic fuzzy topology and its application. Burillo et al.[13] studied the intuitionistic fuzzy relation and their properties. Thakur et.al [44] introduced generalized closed set in intuitionistic fuzzy topology. Various researchers [8, 24, 26, 33, 37, 38] extended the results of generalization of various Intuitionistic fuzzy closed sets in many directions.

The concepts of neutrosophy was introduced by Florentin Smarandache [18, 19, 20] in which he developed the degree of indeterminacy. In comparing with more uncertain ideology, the neutrosophic set can accord with indeterminacy situation. Salama et.al [34,35,36] transformed the idea of neutrosophic crisp set into neutrosophic topological spaces and introduced generalized neutrosophic set and generalized neutrosophic topological Spaces. Ishwarya et.al [22] studied Neutrosophic semi open sets in Neutrosophic topological spaces. Abdel-Basset et.al [1,2,3,4,5,6] gave a novel neutrosophic approach. Many researchers [28, 30, 31, 41, 42] added and studied semi open

sets, α open sets, pre-open sets, semi alpha open sets etc., and developed several interesting properties and applications in Neutrosophic Topology. Several authors [7, 25, 27, 32, 39, 44] have contributed in topological spaces.

Mohana K et.al [29] introduced gsr -closed sets in soft topology in 2017. In this article we tend to provide the idea of NGSR-closed sets and NGSR-open sets. Also, we presented NGSR continuous and NGSR-contra continuous mappings.

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [20] Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic set (NS) A is an object having the form $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ where $\mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x)$ and $\nu_A(x)$ represent the degree of membership, degree of indeterminacy and the degree of nonmembership respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A .

A Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ can be identified as an ordered triple $(\mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x))$ in $]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$ on X .

Definition 2.2. [20] Let $A = \langle \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle$ be a NS on X , then the complement $C(A)$ may be defined as

1. $C(A) = \{ \langle x, 1 - \mu_A(x), 1 - \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$
2. $C(A) = \{ \langle x, \nu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$
3. $C(A) = \{ \langle x, \nu_A(x), 1 - \sigma_A(x), \mu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$

Note that for any two neutrosophic sets A and B ,

4. $C(A \cup B) = C(A) \cap C(B)$
5. $C(A \cap B) = C(A) \cup C(B)$.

Definition 2.3. [20] For any two neutrosophic sets $A = \{ \langle x, \mu_A(x), \sigma_A(x), \nu_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ and $B = \{ \langle x, \mu_B(x), \sigma_B(x), \nu_B(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ we may have

1. $A \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \leq \sigma_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \geq \nu_B(x) \forall x \in X$
2. $A \subseteq B \Leftrightarrow \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \geq \sigma_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \geq \nu_B(x) \forall x \in X$
3. $A \cap B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \vee \nu_B(x) \rangle$
4. $A \cap B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \wedge \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \vee \nu_B(x) \rangle$
5. $A \cup B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \vee \sigma_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \wedge \nu_B(x) \rangle$
6. $A \cup B = \langle x, \mu_A(x) \vee \mu_B(x), \sigma_A(x) \wedge \sigma_B(x)$ and $\nu_A(x) \wedge \nu_B(x) \rangle$

Definition 2.4. [34] A neutrosophic topology (NT) on a non-empty set X is a family τ of neutrosophic subsets in X satisfies the following axioms:

- (NT₁) $0_N, 1_N \in \tau$
- (NT₁) $G_1 \cap G_2 \in \tau$ for any $G_1, G_2 \in \tau$
- (NT₁) $\cup G_i \in \tau \forall \{G_i : i \in J\} \subseteq \tau$

Definition 2.5. [34] Let A be an NS in NTS X . Then

$Nint(A) = \cup \{G : G \text{ is an NOS in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$ is called a neutrosophic interior of A

$Ncl(A) = \cap \{K : K \text{ is an NCS in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K\}$ is called a neutrosophic closure of A

Definition 2.6. [18] A NS A of a NTS X is said to be

- (1) a neutrosophic pre-open set (NPOS) if $A \subseteq Nint(Ncl(A))$ and a neutrosophic pre-closed (NPCS) if $Ncl(Nint(A)) \subseteq A$.

(2) a neutrosophic semi-open set (NSOS) if $A \subseteq NCl(NInt(A))$ and a neutrosophic semi-closed set (NSCS) if $NInt(NCl(A)) \subseteq A$.

(3) a neutrosophic α -open set ($N\alpha OS$) if $A \subseteq NInt(NCl(NInt(A)))$ and a neutrosophic α -closed set ($N\alpha CS$) if $NCl(NInt(NCl(A))) \subseteq A$.

(4) a neutrosophic regular open set (NROS) if $A = Nint(Ncl(A))$ and a neutrosophic regular closed set (NRCS) if $Ncl(Nint(A)) = A$.

Definition 2.7. [22] Consider a NS A in a NTS (X, τ) . Then the neutrosophic semi interior and the neutrosophic

semi closure are defined as

$$Nsint(A) = \cup \{G : G \text{ is a N Semi open set in } X \text{ and } G \subseteq A\}$$

$$Nscl(A) = \cap \{K : K \text{ is a N Semi closed set in } X \text{ and } A \subseteq K\}$$

Definition 2.8. [38] A subset A of a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) is called a neutrosophic α generalized closed ($N\alpha g$ -closed) set if $N\alpha cl(A) \subseteq U$ whenever $A \subseteq U$ and U is neutrosophic α -open in (X, τ) .

3. NGSR closed sets

Definition 3.1. A NS A in a NTS X is stated to be a neutrosophic gsr closed set (NGSR-Closed set) if $Nscl(A) \subseteq U$ for every $A \subseteq U$ and U is a NROS (Neutrosophic Regular Open set) in X .

The complement $C(A)$ of a NGSR-closed set A is a NGSR-open set in X .

Example 3.2. Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_1, G, 1_N\}$ be NT in which $G_1 = \langle x, (0.4, 0.1), (0.3, 0.2), (0.5, 0.5) \rangle$ and $G_2 = \langle x, (0.4, 0.4), (0.4, 0.3), (0.5, 0.4) \rangle$. Here $A = \langle x, (0.4, 0.4), (0.3, 0.2), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle$ is an NGSR-closed set.

Theorem 3.3. Each NCS is a NGSR-closed set in X .

Proof. Let $A \subseteq U$ wherein U is a NROS in X . Let A be an NCS in X .

We got $Nscl(A) \subseteq Ncl(A) \subseteq U$. Consequently A is a NGSR-closed set in X .

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_1, G, 1_N\}$ be an NT having $G_1 = \langle x, (0.4, 0.1), (0.3, 0.2), (0.5, 0.5) \rangle$ and $G_2 = \langle x, (0.4, 0.4), (0.4, 0.3), (0.5, 0.4) \rangle$. Here $A = \langle x, (0.4, 0.4), (0.3, 0.2), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle$ is an NGSR-closed set, however not NCS.

Theorem 3.5. Each $N\alpha$ – closed set is a NGSR-closed set in X .

Proof. Let $A \subseteq U$ in which U is a NROS in X . Let A be an $N\alpha$ – closed set in X .

Now $Nscl(A) \subseteq N \subseteq cl(A) \subseteq U$. Consequently A is a NGSR-closed set in X .

Example 3.6. Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_1, G, 1_N\}$ be an NT in which

$$G_1 = \langle x, (0.6, 0.2), (0.1, 0.5), (0.5, 0.4) \rangle \text{ and } G_2 = \langle x, (0.5, 0.3), (0.3, 0.2), (0.6, 0.4) \rangle$$

Here $A = \langle x, (0.6, 0.3), (0.1, 0.6), (0.5, 0.4) \rangle$ is an NGSR-closed set, but not $N\alpha$ -closed set as

$$Ncl(Nint(Ncl(A))) = C(A) \not\subseteq A.$$

Theorem 3.7. Each Nsemi-closed set is a NGSR-closed set in X .

Proof. Suppose A is an Nsemi-closed set and $A \subseteq U$ wherein U is a NROS in X . Now $(A) = A \cup Nint(Ncl(A)) \subseteq A \cup A = A$. Therefore A is a NGSR-closed set in X .

Example 3.8. Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_1, G, 1_N\}$ be an NT in which

$$G_1 = \langle x, (0.4, 0.5), (0.3, 0.2), (0.5, 0.5) \rangle \text{ and } G_2 = \langle x, (0.4, 0.4), (0.4, 0.3), (0.5, 0.4) \rangle$$

Then $A = \langle x, (0.4, 0.4), (0.3, 0.2), (0.4, 0.5) \rangle$ is an NGSR-closed set, however not Nsemi-closed set as $Nint(Ncl(A)) = G_1 \not\subseteq A$.

Theorem 3.9. Each $N\alpha G$ - closed set is a NGSR-closed set in X .

Proof. Let $A \subseteq U$ where U is a NROS in X . Let A be an $N\alpha G$ - closed set in X . Now $Nscl(A) \subseteq N\alpha cl(A) \subseteq U$. Therefore A is a NGSR-closed set in X .

Example 3.10. Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_1, G, 1_N\}$ be an NT where

$$G_1 = \langle x, (0.6, 0.2), (0.1, 0.5), (0.5, 0.4) \rangle \text{ and } G_2 = \langle x, (0.5, 0.3), (0.3, 0.2), (0.6, 0.4) \rangle$$

Then $A = \langle x, (0.6, 0.3), (0.1, 0.6), (0.5, 0.4) \rangle$ is an NGSR-closed set but not $N\alpha G$ -closed set.

Remark 3.11. The counter examples shows that NGSR-closed set is independent of NPCCS.

Example 3.12. Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_1, G, 1_N\}$ be an NT where

$$G_1 = \langle x, (0.6, 0.2), (0.1, 0.5), (0.5, 0.4) \rangle \text{ and } G_2 = \langle x, (0.5, 0.3), (0.3, 0.2), (0.6, 0.4) \rangle$$

Here $A = \langle x, (0.6, 0.3), (0.1, 0.6), (0.5, 0.4) \rangle$ be an NGSR-closed set, but not NPCCS as $Ncl(Nint(A)) = C(B) \not\subseteq A$.

Example 3.13. Let $X = \{a, b\}$ and $\tau = \{0_1, G, 1_N\}$ be an NT where

$$G_1 = \langle x, (0:5; 0:4), (0:3; 0:2), (0:5; 0:6) \rangle, G_2 = \langle x, (0:8; 0:7), (0:4; 0:3), (0:2; 0:3) \rangle \text{ and}$$

$$G_3 = \langle x, (0:2; 0:1), (0:3; 0:2), (0:8; 0:9) \rangle$$

Then $A = \langle x, (0.5, 0.3), (0.3, 0.2), (0.5, 0.7) \rangle$ is an NPCCS, but not NGSR-closed set.

Theorem 3.14. Consider a NTS (X, τ) . Then for each $A \in$ NGSR-closed set and for each $B \in$ NS in X , $A \subseteq B \subseteq Nscl(A)$ implies $B \in$ NGSR-closed in (X, τ) .

Proof. Assume that $B \subseteq U$ and U is a NROS in (X, τ) which shows that $A \subseteq B, A \subseteq U$. Via speculation, $B \subseteq Nscl(A)$. Consequently $Nscl(B) \subseteq Nscl(Nscl(A)) = Nscl(A) \subseteq U$, given that A is an NGSR-closed set in (X, τ) . As a result $B \in$ NGSR-closed in (X, τ) .

Theorem 3.15. Consider a NROS A and a NGSR-closed set in (X, τ) , then A is a NSemi-closed set in (X, τ) .

Proof. Due to the fact $A \subseteq A$ and A is a NROS in (X, τ) , Via speculation, $Nscl(A) \subseteq A$.

However $A \subseteq Nscl(A)$. Therefore $Nscl(A) = A$. Consequently A is a NSemi-closed set in (X, τ) .

Theorem 3.16. Let (X, τ) be a NTS. Then for each $A \in$ NGSR-open X and for every $B \in$ NS(X), $Nsint(A) \subseteq B \subseteq A$ implies $B \in$ NGSR-open set in X .

Proof. Let A be any NGSR-open set of X and B be any NS of X . By means of speculation $Nsint(A) \subseteq B \subseteq A$. Then $C(A)$ is a NGSR-closed in X and $C(A) \subseteq C(B) \subseteq Nscl(C(A))$. By using Theorem 3.5, $C(B)$ is a NGSR-closed in (X, τ) . Thus B is a NGSR-Open in (X, τ) . Hence $B \in$ NGSR-open in X .

Theorem 3.17. A NS A is a NGSR-open in (X, τ) if and only if $F \subseteq Nsint(A)$ everytime F is a NRCS in (X, τ) and $F \subseteq A$.

Proof. **Necessity:** Assume that A is a NGSR-open in (X, τ) and F is a NRCS in (X, τ) such that $F \subseteq A$. Then $C(F)$ is a NROS and $C(A) \subseteq C(F)$. Via speculation $C(A)$ is a NGSR-closed set in (X, τ) , we've $Nscl(C(A)) \subseteq C(F)$. Therefore $F \subseteq Nsint(A)$.

Sufficiency: Let U be a NROS in (X, τ) such that $C(A) \subseteq U$. By hypothesis, $C(U) \subseteq \text{Nsint}(A)$. Consequently $\text{Nscl}(C(A)) \subseteq U$ and $C(A)$ is an NGSR-closed set in (X, τ) . Thus A is a NGSR-open set in (X, τ) .

Theorem 3.18. A is Nsemi-closed if it is both Nsemi-open and NGSR-closed.

Proof. Considering A is each Nsemi-open and NGSR-closed set in X , then $\text{Nscl}(A) \subseteq A$. We additionally have $A \subseteq \text{Nscl}(A)$. Accordingly, $\text{Nscl}(A) = A$. Therefore, A is an Nsemi-closed set in X .

4 On NGSR-Continuity and NGSR-Contra Continuity

Definition 4.1. Let f be a mapping from a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) to a neutrosophic topological space (Y, σ) . Then f is referred to as a neutrosophic gsr-continuous(NGSR-continuous) mapping if $f^{-1}(B)$ is a NGSR-open set in X , for each neutrosophic-open set B in Y .

Theorem 4.2. Consider a mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$. Then (1) and (2) are equal.

(1) f is NGSR-continuous

(2) The inverse image of each N-closed set B in Y is NGSR-closed set in X .

Proof. This can be proved with the aid of using the complement and Definition 4.1.

Theorem 4.3. Consider an NGSR-continuous mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$ then the subsequent assertions hold:

(1) for all neutrosophic sets A in X , $f(\text{NGSRNcl}(A)) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(f(A))$

(2) for all neutrosophic sets B in Y , $\text{NGSRNcl}(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Ncl}(B))$.

Proof. (1) Let $\text{Ncl}(f(A))$ be a neutrosophic closed set in Y and f be NGSR-continuous, then it follows that $f^{-1}(\text{Ncl}(f(A)))$ is NGSR-closed in X . In view that $A \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Ncl}(f(A)))$, $\text{NGSRcl}(A) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Ncl}(f(A)))$. Hence, $f(\text{NGSRNcl}(A)) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(f(A))$.

(2) We get $f(\text{NGSRcl}(f^{-1}(B))) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(f(f^{-1}(B))) \subseteq \text{Ncl}(B)$.

Hence, $\text{NGSRcl}(f^{-1}(B)) \subseteq f^{-1}(\text{Ncl}(B))$ by way of changing A with B in (1).

Definition 4.4. Let f be a mapping from a neutrosophic topological space (X, τ) to a neutrosophic topological space (Y, σ) . Then f is known as neutrosophic gsr-contra continuous(NGSR-contra continuous) mapping if $f^{-1}(B)$ is a NGSR-closed set in X for each neutrosophic-open set B in Y .

Theorem 4.5. Consider a mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$. Then the subsequent assertions are equivalent:

(1) f is a NGSR-contra continuous mapping

(2) $f^{-1}(B)$ is an NGSR-closed set in X , for each NOS B in Y .

Proof. (1) $\Rightarrow$ (2) Assume that f is NGSR-contra continuous mapping and B is NOS in Y . Then B_c is an NCS in Y . It follows that, $f^{-1}(B_c)$ is an NGSR-open set in X . For this reason, $f^{-1}(B)$ is an NGSR-closed set in X .

(2) $\Rightarrow$ (1) The converse is similar.

Theorem 4.6. Consider a bijective mapping $f : (X, \tau) \rightarrow (Y, \sigma)$. from an

NTS(X, τ) into an NTS(Y, σ). If $Ncl(f(A)) \subseteq f(NGSRint(A))$, for each NS B in X , then the mapping f is NGSR-contra continuous.

Proof. Consider a NCS B in Y . Then $Ncl(B) = B$ and f is onto, by way of assumption, $f(NGSRint(f^{-1}(B))) \subseteq Ncl(f(f^{-1}(B))) = Ncl(B) = B$. Consequently, $f^{-1}(f(NGSRint(f^{-1}(B)))) \subseteq f^{-1}(B)$. Additionally due to the fact that f is an into mapping, we have $NGSRint(f^{-1}(B)) = f^{-1}(f(NGSRint(f^{-1}(B)))) \subseteq f^{-1}(B)$. Consequently, $NGSRint(f^{-1}(B)) = f^{-1}(B)$, so $f^{-1}(B)$ is an NGSR-open set in X . Hence, f is a NGSR-contra continuous mapping.

5. Conclusion and Future work

Neutrosophic topological space concept is used to deal with vagueness. This paper introduced NGSR closed set and some of its properties were discussed and derived some contradicting examples. This idea can be developed and extended in the real life applications such as in medical field and so on.

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